

SYNONYMS ARE A USEFUL WAY TO ADD SOME VARIATION TO YOUR LANGUAGE

1. Research advisor: The teacher of Navai State Pedagogical Institute

Gapparova Mehribon Tulqinovna

2. Student:

Kholdaraliyeva Sevara

Annotation This article discusses the usage and importance of synonyms in English and explains them through examples.

Key words: synonym, different types of synonyms, advanced levelled synonyms of common words.

“A synonym is a word, morpheme, or phrase that means exactly or nearly the same as another word, morpheme, or phrase in a given language. For example, in the English language, the words begin, start, commence, and initiate are all synonyms of one another: they are synonymous. Synonyms (from Greek “syn” and “onym” – “together” and “name”) are the words that have a common meaning (the same denotative meaning) and an additional (connotative) meaning (expressive, stylistic features). are different words”¹.

Synonyms are a useful way to add some variation to your language when you’re writing or speaking in longform. It can be easy to fall into the trap of repeating the same word over and over again. That’s why, it’s always a good idea to have synonyms ready to keep your language fresh. “Synonyms often have very slight differences in meaning, which sometimes means one is more appropriate than another one in a given context”². In fact, there are cases where a synonym might even be a better choice than the original word you’ve chosen.

For example, let look at synonyms of “happy”

- When she won in the race, she was happy

¹ Google.uz

² Ziyonet.uz

- When she won in the race, she was cheery
- When she won in the race she was contented.

Synonyms occur in a language in different contexts, such as formal and informal language, like you'd use in conversation vs. a business or academic paper. Also, some synonyms have slightly different connotations when they're used, even though they might mean the same thing. For example, look at the differences between the terms for ask:

- ask-to put a question to get someone to do something
- demand -to ask firmly for something
- beg- to ask someone in an emotional way to do something or give something
- request-to ask for something politely or formally

which all occur in different contexts and levels of formality.

It is vital for a language learner to learn at least 5 synonyms of common words. If u repeat the same word over and over again during your speech, it automatically decreases your level in speaking tests. Moreover, on a daily basis, you should avoid using the same word repeatedly, and expand your vocabulary.

If candidates want to achieve higher results in English, they should abandon low-level words (such as, like, important, happy) Instead of them, there are myriad of high level word on the internet, and you can find from other sources as well. For instance, rather than using the word “like” in our speech, it is appropriate to use its stronger equivalents:

- I am keen on...
- I am fond of...
- I am enthusiastic about...
- I am passionate about...
- I am really into...
- I am crazy about...
- I am fan of...

There are numerous of synonyms for the word “like”. If you want to talk about your favourite hobby, the above-mentioned phrases will come in handy. These words will give you more points. But when it comes to the usage of synonyms, it is crucial to learn grammatical structure. For example:

“I am keen on swimming”

Not “I am keen on swim”

Many students learn the synonyms, but can’t use them in their speech or they use them incorrectly. It would be better if we don’t use the same word frequently and use the word which has the exact or near meaning.

The synonyms of the word “harmful” are as follows:

- Damaging
- Injurious
- Detrimental
- Noxious
- Hazardous
- Deleterious

To conclude, it should be noted that when you can distinguish synonyms from each other, understand which synonym option is used in which situations, and use them correctly, you can learn a foreign language without any difficulties. You will learn and become a mature staff in the future.

Useful websites:

1. Google.uz
2. Ziyonet.uz